

ELECTRONIC PACKAGING MOVEMENT SENSOR IN AN INTELLIGENT PACKAGING SYSTEM

Gojko Vladić¹, Marko Ađin¹, Nemanja Kašiković¹, Gordana Bošnjaković¹, Magdolna Pal¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of technical sciences, Novi Sad, Serbia

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.17302246

vladicg@uns.ac.rs

Abstract: *Intelligent packaging systems utilize technology to enhance traditional packaging functions, usually in order to enhance customer experience by improving quality, safety, and integrity during transit. One of the potential applications is to track the movement of packages along a supply chain by incorporating movement-sensing technologies, which can monitor the state of a package, the environment around it, and interactions between them. Packaging movement sensors are primarily used to track the physical movement of packages, providing real-time information about their location and conditions during transit. This paper presents the steps in the development and practical application of a packaging movement sensor based on commonly used electronic components. In contrast to drop/tip and tell sensors, an accelerometer-based sensor can actively detect and log movement and changes in position during transport as 3-axis data for later analysis, offering valuable information not only for the user's benefit but also for the improvement of the packaging design.*

Keywords: packaging, movement sensor, intelligent packaging, mishandling.

1 INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for enhanced product quality, safety, and consumer engagement has driven rapid advancements in the field of smart packaging. Unlike traditional packaging, which primarily serves a protective and informational role, smart packaging integrates innovative technologies that actively monitor, communicate, and sometimes even respond to changes in the product or its environment. Smart packaging can have a variety of features or uses, but overall, it has two categories, namely active packaging and intelligent packaging (Young et al., 2020). Active packaging interacts with the product/environment (e.g., moisture absorbers, oxygen scavengers), preventing the growth of pathogens and destructive microorganisms, preventing the transport of pollutants, and extending the shelf-life while preserving the safety and quality of the product. Intelligent packaging monitors, senses, and communicates information through electronic, mechanical, chemical, electrical, or online technologies (e.g., sensors, indicators, data tags) (Ozcan, 2020).

Intelligent packaging systems are focused on improving packaging functions in order to meet increasing regulatory requirements regarding waste reduction, safety, reliability, and also growing consumer demands. This aligns with the broader Industry 4.0 trends, where digitalization and sensor technologies are increasingly applied and integrated into product supply chains (Punia et al., 2023). In order to support all the requirements wide range of intelligent packaging technologies are being developed, such as time and temperature indicators, freshness sensors, movement sensors, and interactive digital labels.

Movement sensors have emerged as a promising solution for addressing specific packaging challenges related to product safety, authenticity, and logistics. The integration of movement sensors into

packaging enables the detection and recording of physical handling events, including shocks, vibrations, tilting, and unauthorized opening. Such functionality is particularly relevant for sensitive products like pharmaceuticals, perishable foods, and high-value consumer goods, where inappropriate handling can lead to quality degradation, reduced efficacy, or economic losses.

Applications for movement-sensor-based packaging extend beyond product protection. They provide valuable data for logistics optimization, supply chain transparency, and consumer trust. For example, by recording irregular handling during transportation, stakeholders can identify weak points in distribution networks, enforce accountability, and enhance overall efficiency. Furthermore, consumers benefit from real-time access to information regarding the handling history of products, which strengthens confidence in brand integrity and safety (Osmólska et al., 2022).

Adoption of movement sensors in packaging still faces challenges, including cost-efficiency, sensor miniaturization, energy consumption, and integration with existing supply chain systems. Ongoing research therefore focuses on the development of low-power sensor platforms, wireless data transmission, and smart materials that can seamlessly incorporate sensing elements.

1.1. Overview of movement sensors applicable in intelligent packaging

Movement sensors applicable in intelligent packaging can be divided into two groups: electronic movement sensors and analog movement sensors. Electronic sensors are digital/semiconductor-based and allow direct data logging, integration with microcontrollers or wireless modules. They offer precision, miniaturization, and connectivity options. In practice, electronic sensors are used in high-value goods packaging (pharmaceuticals, electronics, and luxury items) because of their relatively high price per unit (Unander, 2011).

Electronic movement sensors can be grouped by their construction into:

- accelerometers (3-axis MEMS digital accelerometer),
- gyroscopes (MEMS gyroscope for measuring angular velocity),
- inertial measurement units (combines 3-axis accelerometer and 3-axis gyroscope, 9-axis IMU with built-in sensor fusion),
- vibration sensors (piezoelectric vibration sensors, MEMS vibration sensors), and
- tilt/orientation sensors (MEMS tilt sensors, capacitive inclination sensors).

Analog movement sensors are simpler, can be passive, and respond to physical motion without requiring digital processing. They are lower-cost compared to the electronic sensors and are more common in low-cost logistics packaging. Less precise and most often indicate one time movement over certain threshold, their design prioritizes simplicity and disposability more than data logging.

Analog movement sensors can be grouped by ... into:

- mercury tilt switches (obsolete in most applications due to toxicity),
- ball tilt sensors (contain a small conductive ball that rolls inside a cylinder, making or breaking an electrical connection),
- spring vibration/shock sensors (small springs inside a casing that close a circuit when jolted),
- piezoelectric discs (generate voltage in response to vibration or bending), and

- mechanical impact indicators (purely mechanical, irreversible color-changing labels that indicate when a package has been dropped, mishandled or tilted beyond a set angle).

Table 1: Comparison of motion sensors for Intelligent Packaging

<i>Sensor Type</i>	<i>Precision</i>	<i>Cost</i>	<i>Power Requirement</i>	<i>Suitability for Packaging</i>
<i>MEMS Accelerometer</i>	<i>High</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Best for active monitoring</i>
<i>Gyroscope</i>	<i>Very High</i>	<i>Higher</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>Advanced applications</i>
<i>Piezoelectric Vibration</i>	<i>Medium</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Passive or low</i>	<i>Good for shock detection</i>
<i>Ball Tilt Sensor</i>	<i>Very Low</i>	<i>Very Low</i>	<i>Passive</i>	<i>Simple tilt/tamper detection</i>
<i>Mechanical Shock/Tilt Indicators</i>	<i>Low</i>	<i>Very Low</i>	<i>Passive</i>	<i>One-time-use, low-cost</i>

This paper aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of how electronic movement-sensing technologies can enhance packaging functionality and support sustainable, transparent, and consumer-centric supply chains. Development of the motion sensor prototype, applicable mainly to high-value consumer goods, was used in order to explore the role of movement sensors in intelligent packaging, emphasizing their principles of operation, potential applications across industries, and the challenges that must be overcome for widespread implementation. In this context, the present study explores the application of movement sensors in intelligent packaging, with particular emphasis on the use of the ADXL345 accelerometer as a practical and cost-effective solution.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The intelligent packaging prototype was developed using the common low cost electronic components. Movement sensor selected for this study was ADXL345 Accelerometer, as it is a small, low-power, three-axis digital accelerometer capable of measuring acceleration in the range of ± 2 g to ± 16 g. It provides high-resolution (13-bit) output data and is optimized for applications where low power consumption and high sensitivity are required. Its digital output is available via both I²C and SPI interfaces, making it suitable for integration with a wide range of microcontrollers and wireless modules. ESP32 CH340C with USB-C Microcontroller unit for data acquisition and processing. WROOM-32 Wireless communication module (Bluetooth or Wi-Fi) for transmitting sensor data to an external device. Power source (lithium polymer battery 602040, 500 mAh) optimized for low-energy operation with TP4056 constant-current/constant-voltage linear charger. Casing (custom 3D printed PLA polymer container) in which the sensor unit was embedded.

System Architecture:

- accelerometer ADXL345,
- microcontroller unit ESP32 CH340C,
- wireless communication module WROOM-32, and
- power source (602040, 500 mAh) & TP4056.

Figure 1: Final assembly of the packaging motion sensor prototype

Sensor ADXL345 was mounted on a small, printed circuit board via a pin header for added modularity and placed in the 3D printed casing, which was fixed to the packaging inner wall. Initial calibration was performed to establish baseline acceleration values when the package was at rest. Data acquisition was done by MCU, which collected real-time data from the accelerometer at a sampling rate of 100 Hz. Motion data were transmitted wirelessly to a central monitoring unit using Serial Bluetooth Terminal software by Kai Morich, the collected data, as shown in Figure 2, was transferred to the PC for further analysis using Microsoft Excel.

Figure 2. Raw data transferred from the device

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Collected data was analyzed to assess the frequency and intensity of movement during transportation. Threshold-based algorithms were implemented to identify abnormal events such as impacts (a sharp spike in acceleration magnitude, 2-3 g above gravity, spike duration less than 100 ms to distinguish from longer), drops (free fall net acceleration ≈ 0 g, followed by a sudden impact spike, within a 200 ms), there was possibility for detection of prolonged vibrations (repetitive oscillations around gravity) but it was not tested. In order to capture overall motion and reduce orientation dependency, vector magnitude can be calculated. To reduce false positives minimum time separation between events was required and axis dominance was monitored. Figure 3 shows three independent identified drop events where the vertical Z-axis is represented by green color. Noticeable changes in vertical direction are present as expected in the drop scenario. Significantly less movement is detected in X and Y directions as they represent the initial shock and stabilization of the packaging after the fall.

Figure 3. Three drop events where vertical Z-axis is green, X-axis is blue and Y-axis is red

The results from the test where the packaging was dropped from approximately the same height three times, shown in Figure 4, indicate that three lines representing the Z-axis are similar, inferring repeatability of measurements.

Figure 4. Comparison of Z-axis measurements for three similar drops

The results from the prototype system demonstrate that the ADXL345 accelerometer is capable of effectively detecting and quantifying movement events within intelligent packaging applications, and the selectable measurement ranges provided flexibility for monitoring.

One of the major advantages of the ADXL345 is its low power consumption, which extends battery life and makes it suitable for long-duration shipments. This could be further enhanced with additional modularity of the system regarding the memory and battery capacity. The digital communication interface simplifies communication with microcontrollers and wireless modules, facilitating the development of cost-effective solutions, especially in the case of multi-use packaging.

However, several potential limitations were observed. Battery capacity remains a challenge, especially for extended monitoring in global supply chains, shipping first and foremost. Threshold-based algorithms are efficient in experimental conditions. With additional machine learning techniques, they may be able to capture complex handling patterns far more efficiently. The reliability of wireless communication may decrease in environments with significant electromagnetic interference, so reliable internal data storage may be needed as backup, which can be a problem for extended monitoring.

Despite these challenges, the integration of electronic movement sensors into intelligent packaging provides a significant improvement in mishandling diagnostics over analog movement sensors and traditional passive packaging. By enabling real-time packaging monitoring and data logging, researchers could provide valuable information for the packaging designers alongside ensuring enhanced transparency, accountability, and trust in the supply chain.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the feasibility and potential of using the ADXL345 accelerometer as a core component of intelligent packaging solutions. The sensor enables accurate monitoring of product handling through wireless data communication for remote supervision. These features make intelligent packaging with movement sensors a promising tool for industries where product integrity and safety are critical, as well as provide valuable information for packaging designers to improve product protection features of the packaging. Future work should focus on integrating machine learning algorithms for advanced event classification and scaling the system for industrial deployment.

Acknowledgments: *This research has been supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation through Contract No. 451-03-136/2025- 03/200156.*

5 REFERENCES

Impactograph (2025) How Impact Sensor Technology and Shock Data Loggers Prevent Shipping Damage, <https://impactograph.com/how-impact-sensor-technology-and-shock-data-loggers-prevent-shipping-damage>, Accessed on 15.08.2025.

Osmólska, E., Stoma, M., Starek-Wójcicka, A. (2022) Application of Biosensors, Sensors, and Tags in Intelligent Packaging Used for Food Products—A Review. *Sensors*, 22, 9956.

Ozcan A., (2020) New approaches in smart packaging technologies, 10th International Symposium on Graphic Engineering and Design GRID 2020, pp. 21-37.

Punia Bungar S., Sharma N., Trif M. and Adeel M. (2023) Editorial: Emerging active, smart and intelligent packaging solutions in the fourth phase of the industrial revolution (Industry 4.0). *Front. Nutr.* 10.

Theengineeringprojects (2025) ADXL345 3-Axis Digital Accelerometer <https://www.theengineeringprojects.com/2025/02/adxl345-3-axis-digital-accelerometer.html> Accessed on 15.08.2025.

Unander, T., (2011) System integration of electronic functionality in packaging application, <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:434473/FULLTEXT01.pdf>, Accessed on 15.08.2025.

Young, E., Miroso, M., Bremer, P. (2020) A Systematic Review of Consumer Perceptions of Smart Packaging Technologies for Food. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 4.